

CHILD
RESCUE

Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

D4.3 - ChildRescue Pilot Experimentation Documentation, Release I

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	The Smile of the Child (SoC)	Greece
	Foundation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children – (Child Focus)	Belgium
	Hellenic Red Cross (REDCROSS)	Greece
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Executive Summary

D4.3 - "ChildRescue Pilot Experimentation Documentation, Release I" reports the results from the first pilot experimentation which include the feedback collected from the participants, as well as an initial evaluation and validation of the overall ChildRescue solution.

The **ChildRescue pilot experimentation** is divided into two parts, the first and the second pilot phase, consisting respectively of: a) simulation/tabletop exercise and b) a field exercise. D4.3 documents the simulation exercises of the first pilot phase, that were conducted during the second semester of 2019 in the premises of each of the **three pilot organisations**. By the time of the exercise, all ChildRescue components were deployed as the integrated ChildRescue platform and were prepared as needed to support the pilot execution.

Three scenarios were provided by the pilot organisations to support the pilot operation; two for the Missing Children Emergency Case (Greece-supported by SoC and Belgium-supported by Child Focus) and one for the Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors (Greece-supported by REDCROSS). The developed scenarios were based **on true facts** to create a plausible environment, but any personal data related to the children were **carefully anonymised**. Members and staff of the pilot organisations participated in the exercise and were supported by the technical partners of ChildRescue consortium. The execution of the tabletop exercise followed the pilot guidelines provided in D4.2. The pilot guidelines also included a provision for the systematic collection of participants' feedback through surveys and the conduction of focus groups. The collected information was used as input for further analysis and the extraction of useful conclusions based on the developed evaluation and validation framework. This information was also used for a preliminary calculation of validation KPIs.

The overall perception of ChildRescue by the organisation members that participated in the exercise was very positive. Despite some comments for improvements in the platform, the participants were willing to adopt ChildRescue in their every-day operations, as they **identified possible benefits** from its use. This feedback will be used for the refinement of the second and final release of the ChildRescue platform.

This deliverable shall serve as a basis for the revision of the pilot guidelines for the operation and evaluation of the second pilot phase. The documentation of the second pilot phase will be included in D4.5 – "ChildRescue Pilot Experimentation Documentation Release II" [M34]. Additionally, the results from D4.3 and D4.5 combined will lead to the final pilot evaluation and assessment in D4.6 – "ChildRescue Pilot Evaluation and Lessons Learnt" [M36].

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Abbreviations List

CRM	Customer Relationship Management
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
EC	European Commission
EKKA	National Centre for Social Solidarity
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
IASC	Inter Agency Standing Committee
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MFC	REDCROSS Multifunctional Center
MCOs	Missing Children Organisations
PBM	Performance Based Management
RFL	Restore Family Links operations by Tracing Department of Redcross
S&R	Search & Rescue
TS	Tracing Service
Tx.x	Task x.x
UMC	Unaccompanied Migrant Children
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

The purpose of D4.3 - "ChildRescue Pilot Experimentation Documentation, Release I" is to document the execution of the first ChildRescue pilots, present input collected from participants, and provide an initial evaluation of the pilots and the ChildRescue solution. The first pilot phase was designed as a separate simulation/tabletop exercise for each of the three pilot organisations. Feedback was gathered individually from each organisation and was used for the assessment of the three pilots as a procedure. Furthermore, the pilot execution provided data required to perform an initial validation of the ChildRescue solution using the performance indicators developed in work done in previous deliverables. User experience from the use of ChildRescue in terms of accessibility and usability has also been examined.

The conclusions of the pilot evaluation presented in this deliverable, shall serve as a basis for the adaptation and redesign of the pilot guidelines for the operation of the second pilot. Additionally, this report provides substantial feedback for the refinement of the implemented ChildRescue platform. The second release of this deliverable in D4.5 – "ChildRescue Pilot Experimentation Documentation Release II" [M34] will contain the documentation and results of the second pilot of ChildRescue and will be used for the final pilot evaluation and assessment in D4.6 – "ChildRescue Pilot Evaluation and Lessons Learnt" [M36].

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The rest of the deliverable is structured as follows:

Section 2 constitutes a high-level overview of the pilots. This overview includes the presentation of the two use cases of ChildRescue that drive the pilots (Missing Children Emergency Case and Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors), the overall pilot scheduling and a brief presentation of the ChildRescue evaluation framework. The section concludes with the preparatory steps that were needed to appropriately setup the ChildRescue platform prior to the pilot execution.

Section 3 presents Pilot 1: Missing Children Emergency Case – Greece that was performed by SoC. It consists of the pilot exercise scenario, the actual execution of the tabletop exercise, the initial pilot evaluation and the next steps towards the second phase of the pilot.

Section 4 concerns Pilot 2: Missing Children Emergency Case – Belgium, performed by Child Focus. It is structured identically to Section 3.

Section 5 is dedicated to Pilot 3: Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors-Greece, performed by REDCROSS. It is structured identically to Section 3.

Section 6 concludes the outcomes of the three pilot exercises and describes forthcoming activities in the context of WP4.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

D4.3 is related to the activities of various tasks of WP4 - "Missing Persons Cases Piloting and Evaluation", concerning the overall planning and operation of pilots, as well as the definition of guidelines and

metrics for the final evaluation of ChildRescue against the pilot’s objectives. This deliverable reports the outcomes of the execution of the first phase of the ChildRescue pilots, as defined in the context of D4.2 - “ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release I”. It uses the ChildRescue Validation Framework developed in D4.1 – “Validation Framework Elaboration” and updated in D4.2 to perform the pilot and platform evaluation. This deliverable plays an important role both for the development activities of WP3, as it provides feedback for the refinement of the platform until its final release in D3.4 - “ChildRescue Platform, APIs and Mobile App, Release II”, as well as for the forthcoming piloting activities of WP4. The results presented here will serve as a basis for improvements in the evaluation methodology and the actual platform, and the design of the second pilot phase, that will be reported in D4.4 – “ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release II”. The second release of this deliverable is scheduled in D4.5 for [M34] and will document the execution of the second pilot phase of ChildRescue. D4.3 combined with D4.5, will provide information required for the final evaluation of ChildRescue pilots in D4.6 - “ChildRescue Pilot Evaluation and Lessons Learnt” [M36].

Figure 1-1 Relation to other WPs/Tasks

Deliverable D4.3 will be publicly available after its submission, as required by the dissemination and data management plan of WP5.

2 Piloting Planning and Preparation

2.1 Pilot Overview

Pilot use cases are used to validate, demonstrate and evaluate the ChildRescue approach. ChildRescue introduces features that will enhance the standard processes of the organisations when handling such cases. The added value of ChildRescue to existing procedures will be assessed through the validation framework during the first and second pilot phase.

Each pilot consists of a scenario which is based on true facts from past cases. The scenario is appropriately formed to make use of all **functionalities** supported by ChildRescue at the time of the exercise execution. Then the pilot scenario is executed by the actors participating in the exercise. The execution is followed by a **focus group** based on a template with **open-ended questions** and supplemented by a **survey** designed for the pilot and platform evaluation. The last step is the actual **pilot evaluation**, which is divided in three parts. The first part is the presentation of collected input and comments by participants. These are followed by an initial calculation of simple statistics from the close-ended questionnaires and extraction of conclusions based on feedback from the open-ended focus groups. Lastly, the KPIs of the validation framework are completed based on the executed exercise. It should be noted that only KPIs that were applicable during the first tabletop exercise are included in the presented results. The rest of the KPIs, concerning the general impact of ChildRescue and public usage of the platform, cannot be calculated inside a simulation environment and will be completed after the public release of ChildRescue, in the context of D4.6.

Two use cases are explored in the ChildRescue demonstrators and supported by the three pilot organisations.

Missing Child Emergency Case: This scenario involves a standard case where a child goes missing from his home, the incident is reported to the hotline, a decision for publication of a public appeal is taken, the community and search parties become engaged, and the child is located and returned to his family. The procedure follows the processes as described in ChildRescue, emphasising the **contribution of the ChildRescue** parallel processes along the way. Processes or events that are outside of the immediate interest of ChildRescue as an enhancement of already existing operations are either omitted or only briefly mentioned.

The actors involved in the process are the following: Missing Child, Parent/Guardian/Relative of the missing child, Visitor, Simple User, Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Member, Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Leader, Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager.

Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors: The participation of REDCROSS in ChildRescue focuses on the discovery and identification of Unaccompanied Migrant Children (UMC) in the European Union (EU). *UMC are considered all foreign national or stateless persons below the age of 18, who either arrive in the EU unaccompanied by a responsible adult or are left unaccompanied after their arrival (UNHCR).* Most UMC come from countries at war and/or poor living conditions and might by default be considered as vulnerable in need of protection and in fear of disappearance.

While the overall objective of the ChildRescue platform is the development of an integrated methodology that will transform research and discovery of disappeared children, REDCROSS

participation, taking into consideration the IASC guidelines and also the long experience of the organisation in the protection of UMC, aims to further act effectively in the case of a disappearance of an UMC as well as build on the **potential to predict and even prevent** UMC disappearance.

The REDCROSS response with regard to UMC might be organised around two main axes:

- Protection services provided in the framework of UMC hosting facilities with the REDCROSS
- The Tracing department's operations to restore family links (RFL)

The involvement of the REDCROSS to ChildRescue is thus transactional with the intension of rendering ChildRescue procedures parallel to the existing REDCROSS mechanisms as an added value, especially when it comes to registration, data transfer, monitoring of the UMC, upgrading networking capacity and coordination of activities (research activities included). The pilot's scenario was initially drafted in 2018, taking also into consideration that when an UMC goes missing, the REDCROSS does not automatically engage on search and rescue activities with its employees and volunteers; unless this is for the vital interest of the UMC involved, such as in case of a major concern about his/her life, like in cases of an emergency (i.e. following a shipwreck) or a disaster. In the framework of the ChildRescue platform, different user groups have been foreseen for the REDCROSS, that can range from case workers and volunteers to facility managers and organisation coordinators, with different access levels and privileges. All users are somehow affiliated to the organisation, since the REDCROSS has its own responding mechanisms and does not involve general public in its activities. In this regard and taking into consideration the requirements of the tabletop scenario, the participants to the first pilot phase where REDCROSS employees within the REDCROSS UMC Accommodation Centers and the Tracing Service. The intention is to further extend participation for the simulation exercise to include also employees within the REDCROSS Multifunctional Center for Refugees as well as certified REDCROSS volunteers.

2.2 General Pilot Scheduling

The ChildRescue pilot scheduling should be aligned with progress made in the development of the platform components and the integration of functionalities. Additionally, prior to the public release, the platform and application should be tested within closed user groups from the organisations. Thus, the ChildRescue pilot operation is divided into two phases: a) simulation/tabletop exercise and b) a field exercise respectively. The simulation exercises were conducted during the second semester of 2019, while the field exercises are planned for the first semester of 2020. The specific pilot planning for each of the organisations is presented in the following sections.

2.2.1 Pilot Plan for SoC

The pilot plan for missing children in Greece by SoC consists of two main parts: the first and the second phase. The first phase for SoC consists of two sub-phases: Phase I.1, internal testing and tabletop exercise (with the involvement of 10-20 people) and Phase I.2, internal testing to a controlled group of about 100 people. During the first phase, the first release of the platform/mobile app was tested, which did not include the volunteer app. The second phase consists of performing a field exercise where the second release of the platform/app will be tested, including the functionalities for volunteers.

Specifically, the time plan and the steps that were and will be followed for the piloting in Greece is:

- [M18] - June 2019: Operation of the first release of the mobile app

- [M19-21] - July – September 2019: Internal testing of the first release of the mobile app and provision of comments to the technical partners
- [M22] - October 2019: Training and simulation/tabletop exercise (one day) on the basis of the developed scenario – testing was conducted in a controlled group of 16 people (the testing included registered and unregistered users and the key actors of the pilot organisation –Case Managers, Network Manager, etc- as well as the technical partners) (Phase I.1)
- [M22-23] - October – November 2019: Modifications to the platform/app by the technical partners
- [M24] - December 2019: Testing to a larger controlled group of volunteers (e.g. 100 people) (Phase I.2) – 2nd tabletop exercise
- [M26] - February 2020: Training (one day) and field exercise (one day) of the beta version of the ChildRescue platform/mobile app that will include also the volunteers' app
- [M27] - March 2020: Final version of the platform/mobile app
- [M29] - May 2020: Public release of the ChildRescue platform/mobile app

2.2.2 Pilot Plan for Child Focus

The pilot plan for missing children in Belgium consists of two main parts: the first and the second phase. The first phase consists of an internal testing and tabletop exercise (with the involvement of 18 people). During the first phase, the first release of the platform/mobile app was tested, not including the volunteer app. The second phase consists of performing a field exercise where the second release of the platform/app will be tested, including the functionalities for volunteers and geo-localisation.

Specifically, the time plan and the steps that will be followed for the piloting in Belgium is:

- [M22] - October 2019: Training and simulation/table top exercise (one day) on the basis of the scenario below – testing was conducted in a controlled group of 16 people (the testing included registered and unregistered users and the key actors of the pilot organisation in this phase – Case Managers and the Coordinator as well as the technical partners through Skype)
- [M25] - January 2020: Training on the updated platform (including the necessary modifications gathered after execution of first pilot)
- [M26] - February 2020: Field exercise of the beta version that will include also the volunteers' app
- [M27] - March 2020: Final version of the platform/mobile app
- [M29] - May 2020: Public release of the ChildRescue platform

2.2.3 Pilot Plan for REDCROSS

The pilot plan for missing children in Greece by REDCROSS consists of two main parts: a tabletop exercise (first phase) and a field/simulation (second phase). In the tabletop exercise, a group of 20 people took part. The simulation exercise is scheduled to be held in February 2020 with a much broader participation and certain functionalities that will be tested, including the version for volunteers.

Timetable/plan and steps

- [M18] - June 2019: Basic introduction and internal operation of the app
- [M19-21] - July – September 2019: Internal testing of the existing part of the mobile app. Comments sharing and modifications by technical partners

- [M22] – October 2019: Training and simulation/tabletop exercise (one day). Twenty participants attended training and tabletop exercise, that are key actors of the pilot organisation; Facility Managers, Case Managers, technical staff from the Social Welfare Division and Tracing department, Network Manager, etc. Technical partners also attended the exercise
- [M22-23] - October – November 2019: Modifications to the platform/app by the technical partners
- [M26] – February 2020: Training (one day) and field exercise (one day/same day) of the beta version of the ChildRescue platform/mobile app
- [M27] - March 2020: Final version of the platform/mobile app
- [M29] - May 2020: Public release of the ChildRescue platform/mobile app

2.3 Evaluation Framework Overview

The objective of the ChildRescue pilots is multifaceted. Pilot operation is a mean to verify the methodology and the provided solution with the objectives of the organisations and their actual operations. Furthermore, the ChildRescue pilots are a great opportunity to get **organisation personnel involved in the project**. These people are intended to become users of the platform and their feedback on the ChildRescue platform and application is crucial for the future adoption of the solution. Thus, **two axes constitute the ChildRescue pilot evaluation**: Firstly, a properly developed validation framework to assess the actual added value of ChildRescue. Secondly, a technical evaluation methodology from the users' side in order to gather feedback from pilot users and optimise the offered solution.

The validation framework guiding pilot activities was initially developed in "D4.1- ChildRescue Validation Framework" and updated in "D4.2- ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release I". No updates have arisen to the validation framework since then. The framework was defined based on the Performance Based Management (PBM) principles [1]. A list of appropriate metrics - Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) - was elicited based on the expected results of organisations from the utilisation of ChildRescue. These KPIs provide a means to measure the actual added value of ChildRescue. Each pilot partner indicated which of the indicators in the initial list are related to the cases they will handle during the real-life piloting. The calculation method and baseline value -wherever available – were presented in D4.2 along with the updated KPIs. **The calculation of quantitative KPIs will require information provided directly from sources such as the ChildRescue platform, the social media of the organisations and registered case data.** Qualitative KPIs, however, as for example 'PI.40- *estimating how much ChildRescue assists the organisations and operators on understanding better the behavioural and navigational patterns behind disappearances*', will be defined with self-evaluation through questionnaires.

Preliminary values of KPIs that could be calculated at this stage, are included in this deliverable, based on data available from the first pilot operation by a closed circle of participants. However, the concrete validation of ChildRescue will take place in the context of D4.6, after the platform and application are publicly released and start supporting real-life cases on [M29].

Technical evaluation entails the assessment of the ChildRescue platform and application in terms of - among others - accessibility, usability, relevance to everyday work within the organisation and data

protection, as perceived by users from the organisations. This information is useful for technical partners to identify challenges, misconceptions and opportunities for improvement of the implemented solution, before it is publicly released on [M29]. The approach towards gathering information for the technical evaluation was presented in D4.2. Both closed and open-ended questions will be employed in order to collect information in a guided way while leaving room for open feedback that may arise during the pilot execution. During the first pilot phase, an open-ended interview guide led the semi-structured focus groups that took place in the three participating pilot organisations (REDCROSS, SoC, Child Focus). Input was also provided through a closed-ended questionnaire for accessibility and usability. For the second pilot phase, an (online) questionnaire for the organisations and a questionnaire for the volunteers, as well as open-ended interview guidelines will be developed based on the analysis of results from the first pilot phase. The focus of the second pilot phase will be the volunteers and their support through the volunteer mobile application, which was not available in the first pilot phase. The questionnaires for the organisations will mainly include multiple choice questions based on the issues raised during the first pilot phase to ensure that reported challenges have been fully addressed.

2.4 Platform Preparation for Piloting

Timely deployment of the integrated collaborative ChildRescue environment was a prerequisite for the execution of the pilots. Access to the first release of the **web application** was provided through the domain <https://platform.childrescue.eu/>, which was accessible by any device with a web browser. From this link, the user could login to an existing account using her credentials. The first version of the mobile application for Android was available on Google app store. Once the users entered the mobile application, they had three options: login to an existing account using their credentials (email and password), register as new user using their email address and password, or skip both the login/registration process and continue as a visitor.

ChildRescue platform was appropriately populated with data required for the execution of the pilots. The organisations had already been registered – with minimum details - by the ChildRescue administrator. Because the pilot scenarios included hosting of unaccompanied migrant minors, one of the organisations registered in the platform supported three hosting facilities (as indicated by the scenario). The tabletop exercises were held at the pilot organisations' premises and consisted of nine to thirteen participants (Table 2-1). The ChildRescue platform was prepared to support the expected users. Demo web user accounts (Case Managers and Facility Managers) had been created for the pilots. Additionally, the users of the mobile applications, had already downloaded the application on their phones and created their accounts. Lastly, some demo cases were registered in the platform prior to the pilots, to facilitate training and pilot execution.

Table 2-1 Participants and location of the tabletop exercises

Piloting organisation	Number of tabletop participants (i.e. number of surveys and focus participants)	Location and date of tabletop exercise group
Smile of the Child	13	Athens, 10.10.2019

Child Focus	9	Brussels, 21.10.2019
Hellenic Red Cross	9	Athens, 11.10.2019

3 Pilot 1: Missing Children Emergency Case – Greece

3.1 Pilot Scenario

The scenario used for the tabletop exercise was initially described in D4.2, but it is also presented here with updated information:

A 16-years old girl, Maria, participates in the five-day school trip to Athens (Lyceum of Argostoli, Kefalonia Island). The school`s hotel is in Palaio Faliro. Every day, the school visited a different place of interest. For Maria, it is the first time to be in the capital city, Athens.

The day that Maria disappeared, the school had visited Acropolis. Then, all together they went for lunch and afterwards they had a free time. Everyone had to be back at 17h00 in order to leave for the hotel. The responsible professor then discovered that Maria was not there. Her friends sitting next to her said that Maria went to the toilet around 16h00. On her seat, her jacket, a backpack and her mobile phone were found. After a quick search of the area, the professor informed Maria`s parents and then the Police Station about the missing child. At 18h15, the police officer reported the missing child and formally informed the parents of the girl. The Police Station activated its forces in the area. However, it was 19h00 and the weather was becoming bad with high winds and heavy rain, while temperature was below 15°C. The rest of the schoolmates were in the bus waiting for any progress.

Figure 3-1 Route from Acropolis to tavern

At 19h30, the responsible teacher returned in the tavern in case Maria would come back and at the same time communicated with the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000 of the Organisation "The Smile of the Child" asking for advice and guidance.

Figure 3-2 Route from Tavern to police station

The Social Worker of the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000 (organisation Case Manager) recorded all the information provided by the responsible professor and then he/she communicated with the parents from whom he/she learned that Maria used to receive negative comments and teasing from her classmates because of her appearance and her mother’s origin, too. The parents were terrified because the last days Maria had expressed her intention to skip/escape from this situation while her parents insisted in participating in the school excursion. The parents added that Maria had regular sessions with a psychologist and she followed an antidepressant treatment.

It is 20h00 and the research of the Police Motorcycle Unit (DI.AS) has no results yet and the Division of Missing Persons of the Hellenic Police and the responsible Prosecutor accept the proposal from the organisation ‘The Smile of the Child’ to activate the Amber Alert Hellas.

Maria’s parents agree and follow the procedures foreseen during this process. At 20h25, the Amber Alert is activated.

ΕΞΑΦΑΝΙΣΗ - MISSING

Photo

MARIA X. 16 years old

Disappeared on 29.03.2019 at 17.00, from
Thision (Athens)

Eyes: Brown – Hair: Brown
Height: 1.60 cm – Weight: 80 Kg
She was last seen wearing black leggings,
white t-shirt, white snickers

Can you help?

☎ 116 000 or 100

Figure 3-3 – Sample of Hellenic Amber Alert

Figure 3-4 – Points of interest for Maria’s search

Until now, the procedures followed are those that are foreseen for every new case occurred in the Operational Emergency Centre of “The Smile of the Child”.

At this stage, new procedures are introduced due to the ChildRescue platform, where each responsible actor is reacting complementarily/ supplementary through the platform.

The actors that was planned to participate were:

- Visitor (Anonymous user): 1-2 persons
- Simple User (Registered user): 1-2 persons
- Search & Rescue Team Member: 1-2 persons
- Volunteer Team Member: 1 person
- Organisation Case Manager: 1 person
- Organisation Network Manager: 1 person
- Organisation Coordinator Manager: 1 person
- Organisation Owner: 1 person

Presence, support and training by representatives of the technical partners was also foreseen.

3.2 Scenario Execution

Firstly, staff members of the pilot organisation (SoC) were trained about the main steps that the actors should follow when using the ChildRescue platform. Therefore, the technical partners conducted a one-day seminar (face to face) during the tabletop exercise (one more is planned to be conducted before the field exercise) that included the main steps that each actor should follow. The content of the training seminar was mainly based on Annex I: End Users’ Handbook of the D4.2. More information, such as the main instructions of the training, will be found in the updated version of the End Users’ Handbook in the context of D4.4, to be delivered on March 2020.

As depicted also on the following table, a total of 9 persons participated in the tabletop exercise from SoC (as well as 4 members of the consortium).

Table 3-1 Overview of the tabletop exercise conducted by SoC

Tabletop	
Time schedule	10 th October 2019
Platform release	1.0
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visitor (Anonymous user): 1 person - Simple User (Registered user): 2 persons - Search & Rescue Team Member: 1 person - Volunteer Team Member: 1 person - Organisation Case Manager: 1 person - Organisation Network Manager: 1 person - Organisation Coordinator Manager: 1 person - Organisation Owner: 1 person <p>Presence, support and training by representatives of the technical partners (4 people), the project coordinator (NTUA – 2 people) and MADE (1 person), who also played the part of citizens receiving notifications, but without sending any feedback.</p>

The Organisation Case Manager enters the case’s information in ChildRescue. An Alert is sent to the users in the area that is defined by a centre and a dynamically changing radius for a duration of 24 hours. The Organisation Coordinator Manager has access to the data.

Figure 3-5 – The Case Manager creates the alert

Figure 3-6 – The alert is available on the app

Three users (two registered and one anonymous), provide feedback via the app.

- 20h40: User A uploads a photo outside the Acropolis Museum with a girl that looks like Maria, but with black shoes and a backpack.

Figure 3-7 – Provided photo from the user

- 20h41: User B texts a message mentioning that Maria was at Monastiraki Station getting on the train with direction to Kifissia. "The girl that you are searching for is inside the train going towards Kifisia. I am not sure if she disembarked at Herakleion station or if she continued. I disembarked at OAKA."

Figure 3-8 – Potential route

- 20h43: User C texts a message referring that Maria was in a clothing store in The Mall Athens.

“I have the impression that the girl that you are searching for is at Marousi Mall and if I am not mistaken, I saw her inside the X store a few minutes before. I am working here as a cashier and she was waiting in order to pay.”

The Case Manager evaluates the feedback and informs Police and in parallel examines the social media and the potential routes. In parallel, the Case Managers feed the system with other information that they receive from citizens or relatives via the 116000 Hotline.

- 21h10: User D sends to the app text informing that from 16.00 – 18.00 outside the Thision station, Maria asked for information about how to go at Piraeus. “I saw Maria at Thision station definitely after 4.30 and before 5.30. She asked me how she can go to Piraeus and I told her to take Line 1 but I think that she did not understand. She was not OK.... She asked me for a ticket but I did not have and I gave her 1 euro; this was what I all had in coins”.

Figure 3-9 – Potential route

- 21h30: User E uploads a photo from Metro station of Ilioupoli, with a girl that resembles with Maria. The user writes: "I am security at Metro station of Ilioupoli. If Maria is the person in the photo, then she is nearby the metro lines and she is not getting in any of the passing trains. I asked her if she needs help but she did not respond and got away from me".

Figure 3-10 – Provided photo from the user

Figure 3-11 – Full view of potential routes

Based on the received evidence, the location area where the alerts are sent is widened, because most probably Maria is not at Acropolis area. Soon, the provided evidence indicates automatically a specific area.

The Network Manager mobilizes the Search and Rescue Team for Missing Children "Thanassis Makris" of the Operational Emergency Center of "The Smile of the Child" that was already in readiness (via the Search & Rescue / Volunteer Team Leader) since 12 rescuers and 2 Canine Teams were already on alert (maximum activation time: one hour). **The Network Manager coordinates and provides guidance to the operational teams via the app** (not conducted in practice because the volunteer app/platform was not ready – will be tested in December 2019 and during the field exercise).

However, a citizen calls at the hotline 116000 and indicates that he saw Maria at the culture centre of Niarchos.

The Network Manager evaluates the evidence. Via the exercise, it was made clear to the participants that until locating the missing child, no area can be excluded from the search.

When Maria is found, the Case Manager, coordinator and owner perform their duties (e.g. closing case, archiving case, case report, notification of app users that the missing person was found, removal of photos etc.).

3.3 Pilot Evaluation

3.3.1 Main Outcomes

In general, the participants found the **platform and app** very useful for their everyday work. They intent to use it and provided valuable feedback. Both the platform and the app are considered to assist the Case Managers and volunteers in their work, it will facilitate the communication with even more citizens in real time, and it will greatly help for the quicker location of a missing child via profiling, multisource analytics and other features.

One main outcome was that the evidence that will be received has to be carefully evaluated and to keep any potential evidence as probable. Only when the child is located one can be sure about the credibility of the provided evidence. The following terms should be differentiated:

Point Last Seen (PLS) - This is the point on the map where the person was last spotted by a witness with a positive identification. It might be a trailhead, hunting camp, boat dock, parking lot, etc. If you know for certain the person was seen standing at by their car in the parking lot just two hours ago, then you have a place to begin your search. You also know about how far the person might be able to travel in two hours, which helps limit your search area.

Last Known Position (LKP) - During a search, clues will turn up about the person. Occasionally, the clue will be solid enough to be reasonably certain the search subject left it. For example, if the person is hiking a trail and searchers have a good unique shoe print, a tracker can often find the same print along the trail, at a stream bed, etc. and know beyond a shadow of a doubt that the person left the clue. Since the LKP is more recent than the PLS, you basically have a new starting point for your search. Knowing just these two points allows you to determine, general direction of travel, approximate speed of travel, etc.

Suggested modifications (Phase I.1, internal testing)

The following comments derive from the Phase I.1 (internal testing) of the platform and app (1st version) to a controlled group of 9 people from SoC (Case Manager, Network Manager, users, volunteers, organisation coordinator, owner).

1. The text regarding GDPR and info about the fact that the user has the ability to register or continue unregistered should be indicated to the users before starting the registration and not after.
2. When you register you provide name, surname, e-mail and password. Then it requests the username and password; the user should somehow know that the user name is the e-mail s/he indicated before.
3. The user should be able to view a bigger photo of the missing child
4. Provide information about location: an explanation should be added that we need the location that was last seen by the user

5. When a user submits the information, a text/pop up window should appear saying something (e.g. thank you for the information you provided)
6. Sometimes the main menu (dashboard) is not available and you cannot return back
7. As a general comment the texts about SoC need revision (e.g. the text for volunteerism)

Changes that were identified from the tabletop exercise

1. If the user has deactivated the GPS, s/he cannot receive an existing alert when s/he turns it on
2. Add a field for age (not only date of birth) (the "age" field should be visible to the public but the date not)
3. Field "Phone number": it should be defined who's phone, missing person's or relative's
4. For the field "Money" and such relevant fields: provide not only a yes/no option but also "unknown"
5. The grades of education should be adapted to the Greek context
6. A help button should be added to several fields that will explain to the Case Managers the information we are asking for in order to ensure a unified use of the platform
7. When the user types the radius, it is good to see on the map the radius in circles
8. The Case Manager should have the option to update an existing alert and not to create new one
9. Add a Desktop notification for the Case Managers, so there will be no need to have the app open all the time
10. When the different locations are received, it is suggested to be able to see them on a map (for the role of the Network Manager)
11. It is necessary to be able to know how many users have received the notifications and how many are active

3.3.2 Feedback Analysis

The usability of the **app** such as size, colour and contrast of the text, audibility of alarm signals as well as the usability in the work and the data protection all had a median outcome of 'very good', which equals the highest score of 5 on the survey. The average absolute deviation (ad) from the median, which indicates how much the single answers differ from the median, was low (ad < 0,5) for most answers, which signifies that the participants were in agreement over their answers. As there were five categories (excluding 'don't know'), 0,5 was set as the border value to decide whether the average absolute deviation from the median renders an explanation, since this would indicate a shift from one category to another for the majority of answers. A higher average absolute deviation from the mean was registered for the choice of text colour in the app (ad= 0,77) and the usability in the everyday work (ad= 0,67). The text colour should thus be revised before the second tabletop exercise to ensure that it allows users with visual impairments to also view content and the usability in everyday work could be demonstrated further in the next exercise as well. The intuitive nature of the app use (ad= 0,46), the navigation within the app (ad= 0,62) and the comprehensibility of the app (ad= 0,42) were all rated as 'good', with a value of 4. This could indicate a high satisfaction with the app in the current form, without major adjustments necessary from the viewpoint of the participants of the Smile of the Child tabletop exercise. However, it should be noted that the volunteer app was not ready by the time of the first tabletop exercise and was consequently not demonstrated to the participants. The usability of the ChildRescue app was rated as 'very good' or 5 as the median for the items 'timely response to

missing cases' (ad= 0,5), 'increasing the speed of recovery of missing children' (ad= 0,55), 'matching old similar cases to new cases' (ad= 0,6), and 'establishing relevant locations of missing children' (ad= 0,5). However, the average absolute deviation from the median was increased in comparison to the majority of items on the app and platform design, indicating that the participants were not as much in agreement about the usability of the ChildRescue app in their work. Albeit the ad was higher in the usability in work, this does not necessarily exclude the app from being useful as the variance in rating could be due to the different positions held by the participants. Aspects regarding volunteers were rated lower, such as the ability to organise volunteers using the app, which was scored a rating of 'good' or 4 (ad= 0,44) as the median and the possibility to recruit new volunteers through the app, which scored a median of 3,5 (ad= 1), equalling 'okay-good'. The average absolute deviation from the median was especially high for the item 'recruiting new volunteers', since 3,5 was not given as an option and the lack of demonstration of the volunteer version of the app in this specific tabletop exercise may have also led to more confusion and less optimism about the usability of volunteer aspects of the app in the work of the Smile of the Child. This will be addressed in another tabletop exercise of Smile of the Child in December, which will showcase the volunteer app, to ensure that the benefits of the app for working with volunteers are fully understood by all participants.

The **platform** was rated equally high with a 'very good' or 5 as the median in most aspects, including the colour, size and contrast of the text, the usability in everyday work, accessibility to staff members, navigation and intuitive use of the platform and the data protection in place. Only the items 'easy to use' (ad= 0,54) and 'usability in everyday work' (ad= 0,62) had an average absolute deviation from the median that were higher than 0,5, which indicates that not all participants were in agreement with the high rating in those two aspects (easy to use and usability in everyday work). In the rating of the platform, the item 'understandable for volunteers' had a median of 'good' or 4 (ad= 0,43) and the item 'alarm signals are audible' scored 4,5 (ad= 0,87). The relatively high average absolute deviation from the median can partially be explained by the fact that 4,5 was not an option, leading to an increased average absolute deviation since all scores are spread from the median by default. The individual answers varied from 3 to 5, equalling 'okay to very good'.

The median in the rating of the usability of the platform for the work of the piloting organisation was rated as 'very good' or 5 only for the creation of case reports (ad= 0,45). Both the establishment of relevant location of the missing child (ad= 0,67) as well as the increase of the speed of the recovery of the missing child (ad= 0,6) reached a median score of 4,5, equalling 'good to very good'. The organisation of volunteers (ad= 0,6) as well as the timely response to missing cases (ad= 0,5) were both rated 'good' or 4. Lastly, matching old cases to new cases scored the lowest median of 3,5 (ad= 0,9) or 'okay to good' in the questions on the usability of the platform for the work of Smile of the Child. Overall, the platform has received lower median scores than the app, which might indicate that some more explanation on the use and usefulness of the platform should be included in the second tabletop exercise.

The last set of questions on the survey targeted the **current work** of Smile of the Children without the ChildRescue app or platform to gain insight into the time framework for the clearing of missing children cases currently at play. This will be vital for the second tabletop exercise as it will allow a direct comparison between the presumed work efficiency without and with the ChildRescue app and the corresponding platform. Some questions asked about the work experience without the ChildRescue tools, so the current status of the workflow in the organisation. The majority of the participants

answered 'I don't know' to some items, meaning that only a small minority (n) answered with a score at all. The items 'average number of old cases matched to current case' (n= 2), 'average time needed for examining & retrieving information from old similar cases' (n= 2), 'number of investigation activities in irrelevant locations' (n= 2), and 'average time needed for creating complete case reports' (n= 3) were only scored by less than half of the participants. The n indicates the number of answers received on that specific item. Hence, the answers to these items cannot be used for a correct comparison, since there is not a sufficient amount of numerical answers. However, the indication of not knowing these items can be useful for the second survey as well, since it indicates that these are tasks that are not a part of the regular workload of most of the participants and could thus be rephrased. The average time between the reporting and the recovery of a missing child as well as the average time needed for citizens to receive information on a case was estimated to lie between two to five and six to ten hours. The relatively high variation in the individual answers could be explained by the different positions of the participants and their resulting perspectives or estimations of the time needed. The average time needed for the formation of a volunteer search and rescue team was estimated to be two to five hours, with little variation in the individual answers. These values can serve as a comparative value for the second tabletop exercise to gain insight into the changes made with the ChildRescue tools.

The facilitation of a focus group enabled the gathering of more specific in-depth feedback, whereby the attention was placed on the usability of the app and platform and potentially necessary changes. Albeit nobody mentioned lacking features of the app and platform some aspects were identified that should be revised before the second part of the piloting phase is initiated. Participants wish more information for the users. The start screen should include the information that users do not need to register and the general GDPR information which currently pops up during the registration. Additionally, it should be made clear that the user will not receive any notifications if the GPS function of their smartphone is turned off. In the process of registration, the user needs to input their full name, email address and a password. The email address is then used as the 'username' to log into the ChildRescue App without that being made explicit. Hence, the term 'username' for the log-in should either be altered to 'email' or it should be made clear that those are the same. Furthermore, the photo of the missing child should be larger since it is too small to identify the child. When using the option to provide information, there should be an explanation that the location the child was last seen in should be given rather than the current location of the user. After a user has turned in information, an appreciative message should come up in order to keep the motivation for participation high. Participants of the tabletop exercise have also noted that the menu of the app was sometimes not available, which renders it impossible to navigate further in the app or go back to the home screen. Lastly, the text about the Smile of the Child Organisation as currently depicted in the app still requires revision.

Participants mentioned that changes are necessary for the platform. While the date of birth of the child should be displayed on the platform, it should not be visible for the users of the app, so there needs to be the option to also input the age of the child, which then should be the only information shown on the app. It would be useful to indicate the exact type of information needed in the input field through a 'help' tool to ensure that the same information is entered by everybody. For example, in the 'phone number' field, it should be defined whose phone number is entered since it could be the missing child's or the phone of a relative or friend of the missing child. When inputting relevant information on the current status of the child – such as whether it has access to money – there should be also the option to input 'unknown' instead of just 'yes/no'. The grade system currently used in the platform should be

altered to match the Greek education system. In order to increase the usability of the platform for Case Managers in their work life, they should be able to alter an alert if there is new reliable information instead of having to delete and create a new alert. The Case Managers should also be able to see how many users have received notifications and how many of them are actively following the case. Additionally, the Case Managers should also receive a desktop notification, so they do not have to leave the platform and app open constantly. In order to improve the understanding of the location, the user should be able to see the radius they put in on the map as a circle. Also, the Network Managers should be able to see the different locations that were flagged by users on a map.

Despite these numerous – albeit small – alterations to the app and the platform, the participants of the focus group agreed that they would use the ChildRescue platform in their work and also work toward a widespread use of the app through the public in Greece, since they flagged a number of distinct advantages of working with the ChildRescue tools. For the organisation, benefits lie mostly in the enhanced speed, namely in the possibility to quickly create alerts, communicate within the search team and extract case reports, relate the current case to potential earlier instances of the child going missing and the outcome of these cases. Furthermore, the scalability of and complete control over the alert systems, which in turn increases the data protection for the child, was identified as a benefit, since the dissemination of alerts through media channels or social media leaves a higher risk of the alerts not being deleted in a timely fashion or even at all. Additionally, feedback from the users can be evaluated in order to identify unreliable or irrelevant information (for example so-called ‘trolls’) easier. The public, in turn, benefit by being able to quickly provide information without having to know the hotline number and to include videos or photos for better identification. Additionally, they have the possibility to follow cases in their area, which can serve as an incentive to engage more actively with missing children cases. Lastly, the missing children themselves can profit from the faster recovery, as the risk of victimisation for the missing children rises with the time they are unsupervised. Yet, despite the general positive attitude toward the ChildRescue app and platform, the necessity of training of the volunteers in the use of the app through a fictional scenario before they are working on real cases was indicated, which should be taken into consideration. The piloting organisation should draft fitting scenarios for the training of their volunteers.

3.3.3 ChildRescue KPIs based on Pilot

The relevant KPI values, as formed from the execution of the Phase I.1 of the first pilot phase, are enlisted in the following table.

Table 3-2 KPIs for SoC based on first Pilot-Phase I.1

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value	KPI Value after 1st Pilot-Phase I
PI.01	number of ChildRescue mobile application downloads monthly	N/A	0	13
PI.02	number of aggregated	N/A	0	13

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value	KPI Value after 1st Pilot-Phase I
	ChildRescue mobile application downloads			
PI.05	number of notifications sent through ChildRescue and opened	N/A	0	11
PI.06	average number of citizens providing feedback per case	average number of citizens providing feedback per case before mobile application launch (excluding family members)	4	5
PI.07	average number of citizens providing feedback through the ChildRescue app per case	N/A	0	5
PI.09	ratio: average number of citizens receiving notification per case through ChildRescue to total number of mobile application downloads	N/A	0	11/13
PI.10	ratio: number of notifications sent to specific locations to total number of notifications	N/A	0	1
PI.11	ratio: number of relevant (in the context of ChildRescue terminology) feedback to total	N/A	0	5/5

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value	KPI Value after 1st Pilot-Phase I
	number of submitted feedback			
PI.12	ratio: number of mobile app users who visited the relevant informative section in ChildRescue app (Do's & Don'ts, how to respond in case of child neglect, abuse etc.)	N/A	0	11

3.4 Challenges and Next Steps

The ChildRescue platform and app, was assessed as highly beneficial and supplementary to the existing processes. Specifically, it has advantages for a) the organisation, b) the citizens and c) the missing children.

Specifically, the advantages for the organisation will be:

- New alerts: quick creation of an alert
- Ability to extract case reports (quickly & electronically)
- Quick access
 - o Quick search engine in case of multiple disappearances of the same child
 - o Easy access to the platform from multiple users and from users with different profiles/levels of access
 - o Easy changing of the configurations of an active alert or even immediate deactivation (total control of the alert system)
- Encoding of the child's profile (not visible to the public) such as psychosocial status, health status, reasons that led to the disappearance, etc.
- Updates: quick update of information about an open case
- Maintaining of record of feedback from citizens having also the ability to mark their evaluation in the platform (relevant, irrelevant, credible etc.)
- Search and rescue members can access quickly a directory to get search alerts and chat/communicate using the app (different chat rooms)
- Scalable alerts (restricted or wider geographical area of notifications)

The advantages for the citizens:

- Facilitation of the provision of information by the citizens (real time) about a case via the app (not only via the hotline)
- Ability to get informed for missing children in the citizen's area but also at national level

- Citizens can send location information and media (e.g. images, video) via the app
- Real-time alerts prompt users with immediate updates (with the ability to follow or unfollow a case)

The advantages for the missing children

- Ability to remove automatically the information on the app upon case's closure/expiration
- Ability to ensure that all citizens that were informed about the case, all get informed about the closure of the case
- The rights of the child on its personal data, under GDPR, are respected
- The ultimate goal of ChildRescue is to reduce the time period between the moment a child is reported missing and the one it is found

Among the challenges can be included the following:

- The work of the Network Manager can be highly assisted by the availability for free of a Position tracking system of the volunteers during the search and rescue actions
- For profiling that can also assist the search and rescue teams, other material can also be taken into account such as the "Missing Person Behaviour Handbook or the Lost person behaviour handbook".
- Profiling for the cases of abductions cannot be applied
- Due to the GDPR restrictions only public data from social accounts can be examined; however, the authorities always have the option to request break of confidentiality constraints for missing children in danger

Next steps: organise the Phase I.2 of the first pilot phase, namely execution of the 2nd table top exercise in order to test the volunteer app (December 2019) and internal testing of the app by 100 people when a download link is available (and provision of feedback). As a final step, before the onset of the pilot in real cases, a field exercise will be held (February 2020). The results from Phase I.2 and the second pilot phase will be reported in D4.5.

4 Pilot 2: Missing Children Emergency Case – Belgium

4.1 Pilot Scenario

The scenario used for the tabletop exercise was the following as described also in deliverable D4.2.

Officer De Boeck from the Police Zone Wemmel calls the 116000. **Our receptionist, An, receives a call from the officer** upon request from the CPS (The Crown Prosecution Service). The officer mentions that Laura, 14 years old (date of birth 15/09/2005), has been missing since this morning. She was supposedly on her way to school, but never arrived.

She had the following things with her:

- her cell phone – but it is disconnected
- her school bag – but she carried nothing unusual with her (nothing seems missing from her room)
- bank account empty – some cash but total amount unknown
- we are not sure whether she has a pass for public transport. She recently lost it and had to apply for a new one

Together with the officer, An establishes a first profile of Laura:

- Psychological problems
- No medication
- It is unusual for her to disappear without a trace
- She never stayed out longer than permitted
- She never skipped classes
- Social media account inactive during last couple of weeks
- Boyfriend unknown

The officer gives the contact details of the parents. The parents live together.

At 3.30 p.m. the receptionist transfers information orally and via the CRM-system to the Case Manager on duty. The Case Manager creates a case-file in the CRM-system and contacts the police officer. We get more details on what happened to Laura. She left at 7 a.m. to school, not showing any suspicious behaviour. She took her school bag with her. It didn't look like she was carrying more weight than on other days. There was no particular fight the day before. She left, but never arrived at school in Jette, a couple of stops away. She left in the direction of the bus stop. Laura is officially reported as missing and the neighbourhood examination as well as the examination of her cell phone and camera images were negative. We also obtain some more profile clarifications. These last couple of days the parents have noticed some behavioural changes. She has been extremely introvert, hiding in her room and struggling with negative thoughts. Her school performance has deteriorated the last couple of weeks. The school council mentions that she has been very distracted. There have not been any suicide-attempts in the past.

Because of lack of results, the CPS requests diffusion via ChildRescue App. The Federal Office for Missing People has been informed.

At 4 p.m., the Case Manager calls the parents. She informs them about the involvement of Child Focus and checks whether the parents have sufficient emotional support. The Case Manager requests a recent photograph (to be send via mail foto@childfocus.org) and checks the description of the missing girl. The parents are informed about possible media attention and the possibility of deflecting press to the central communication department in Child Focus. Together they evaluate the impact of a public appeal and the parents approve the diffusion via ChildRescue App.

We also obtain extra clarifications but little more is known. Laura has lived quite isolated in her room for the last two weeks. The parents are in touch with Laura's best friends – they are very worried too. Her friends mention the possibility that she might have a boyfriend, but they don't know a lot about him, except that he is a lot older than Laura.

We discuss Laura's hang out spots. She likes to hang out in parks (park next to the Atomium near the movie theatre) and often meets up with friends on place de Mirroir in Jette. When she goes to the city centre, she hangs around Place Saint-Catherine. These last weeks she declined to meet up with friends.

At 4.30 p.m., the Case Manager calls the Federal Office for Missing People. The officer on duty is aware of the diffusion and might follow-up with a press release in the evening news of 7 p.m. Besides the diffusion via ChildRescue, we consider the idea of hanging out posters in her neighbourhood – as last point seen. The officer will bring this idea to the attention of the CPS. The CPS approves. The Case Manager informs the back-up (Organisation Coordinator Manager) and gives input in the ChildRescue app, targeting a 10 km radius around the neighbourhood (Wemmel): Laeken, Jette and city centre Brussels (1000 Brussels).

A total of 16 testimonies (4 anonymous, 12 registered) come in half an hour through the ChildRescue App. The testimonies are opened by receptionist who copies their content into the CRM file and on e-mail or fax to share with the police. Based on the received evidence, the location where the alerts are sent is widened and extended to the whole Brussels area because there is indication that Laura might be at the other side of the city. Soon, the provided evidence indicates automatically a specific area. Another 2 testimonies (1 anonymous, 1 registered) are received through ChildRescue and shared with the police.

The Case Manager gets a report from the police, that based on one of the testimonies, Laura has been located in Jette. The Case Manager closes the case in ChildRescue, and followers are alerted that Laura has been located safe and sound.

Actors

- Visitor (Anonymous user): 3 persons
- Simple User (Registered user): 2 persons
- Organisation Case Manager: 3 persons (1 Case Manager, 1 receptionist who can download testimonies into CRM and send them to police and 1 responsible for posters who can upload the missing child's poster to Child Rescue)
- Organisation Coordinator Manager: 1 person

- Organisation Owner: 1 person

4.2 Scenario Execution

On October 22nd 2019, the day started with a training of the staff members of Child Focus about the main steps that the actors should follow when using the ChildRescue platform, by the technical partners. The content of the training seminar was mainly based on Annex I: End Users' Handbook of the D4.2.

As depicted also in the following table, a total of 10 persons participated in the tabletop exercise, from Child Focus personnel. Additionally, six persons from the technical partners participated as citizens, but did not take part in the surveys.

Table 4-1 Overview of the tabletop exercise conducted by Child Focus

Tabletop	
Time schedule	22 nd October 2019
Platform release	1.0
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visitor (Anonymous user): 3 persons - Simple User (Registered user): 2 persons - Organisation Case Manager: 3 persons - Organisation Coordinator Manager: 1 person - Organisation Owner: 1 person <p>Web presence, support and training by representatives of the technical partners (4 people) and the project coordinator (NTUA – 2 people), who also played the part of citizens receiving notifications, but without sending any feedback.</p>

The organisation Case Manager enters the case's information in ChildRescue. An Alert is sent to the users in the area that is defined by a centre. The Organisation Coordinator Manager has access to the data.

Not all users received notifications on the mobile phones through the ChildRescue app. For some of them it was enough to turn on their location services on their device, one user never got the notification.

4 users (2 registered and 2 anonymous), provide feedback via the app.

- User A and B provided a solely text-based testimony having seen the girl in a park in Brussels.
- User C and D uploaded pictures to support their text-based testimony.

The Case Manager changes the radius of the area of publication. This worked technically perfect on the platform but could not be tested with the application, since this was a tabletop exercise in which the participants did not change location.

The Case Manager gets a report from the police, that based on one of the testimonies, Laura has been located in Jette. The Case Manager closes the case in ChildRescue, and followers were alerted that Laura has been located safe and sound.

4.3 Pilot Evaluation

4.3.1 Main Outcomes

The participants of the pilot were very positive about the ChildRescue platform and application. They found it easy to use and user friendly. They also see an added value in the use of the ChildRescue tools, especially when it comes to its potential reach and user-friendliness in providing testimonies.

Important questions / concerns that have been raised were the following:

- The anonymity of simple users. If we get a testimony now (via 116000), there is always a phone number provided, if something is not clear we, the police or prosecutor can always call that person to get more information.
- We should have the possibility to draft alert in ChildRescue only using the first name (and thus without the last name) of the child.
- Can we make an automated link between the ChildRescue platform and our own CRM?
- We have to be able to send the testimonies that come in through ChildRescue to the police in an easy manner. Can you print them out? Can you mail them? Can you attach them? It is our policy not to check testimonials but to forward them all, so we have to be able to get them out of the platform somehow, in a way that allows editing, because you still need to be able to translate, for example. The best thing would be a mail option: clicking the testimony would generate automatically an email. Ideally, you should be able to enter in the platform for which police zone the testimonies are intended, with the e-mail address, so that each testimonial can be sent via the e-mail option after our check to the e-mail address linked to the file.
- Bilingualism. For example, for Brussels we make alerts in French and Dutch. Would this mean we have to create two separate cases, as the information for the alert is automatically generated via the case description. So, if you fill in the case in Dutch, the data will be in Dutch. What if we need a French appeal? Ideally this would be automated so it would be possible to fill in data in two languages, to be able to choose in the same case in which language you put your data in the appeal. Another very valid option would be the get a preview of the alert, that we can still edit, for example a different name on alert than in the file or manually type in the other language in that alert.

More practical issues raised were the following:

- Many lines cannot be fully read (e.g. Arrival at the facility: 'if the child has been')
- Reasons of disappearance: maybe add school issues as a category?
- Problems with saving a new case/make it possible to save during the process?
- Social media: more options (Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram, etc.) + the possibility to check several boxes
- Working in and saving by more than 1 Case Manager in one case: problem of overwriting.
- Save button visible at all times

- Haircut in description
- Demographic data: languages spoken (what languages), postal code (important for Brussels)
- Psychological data: add Parent/Child dispute
- Provide possibility to link cases (per ex. Two runaways, girl and his boyfriend)
- Possibility to download the preview and/or send it to colleagues
- When you go to the dashboard, it looks like the cases are randomly put next to each other. Maybe there is a clearer view? For example: all resolved/closed cases below and the active/urgent ones on top? During the pilot, some closed cases came before active ones.
- Will there be a consent form/user guidelines that have to be agreed to when downloading the app?

4.3.2 Feedback Analysis

During the first tabletop exercise at Child Focus a focus group and surveys were conducted with 9 out of the 10 persons from Child Focus personnel (N=9). The overall median scores in the Child Focus group were in the middle between the other two piloting organisations, however, 17 items were answered with 'I don't know' by the majority of the participants, which is a lot higher than in the other two organisations (five in the Smile of the Child group and one in the Hellenic Red Cross). While the indication of not knowing is in itself a valid outcome, it indicates that some topics should be revisited in more detail throughout the second tabletop exercise to ensure that all participants have a full understanding of the ChildRescue tools and their opportunities for the everyday work.

In the evaluation of the app in terms of accessibility, two items were not answered with a score by the majority of the participants, namely 'protecting sensitive data' (n= 2) and 'alarm signals audible' (n= 4). All the other items, namely the size (ad= 0,33), colouring (ad= 0,33) and contrast of the text (ad= 0,22), as well as the accessibility in everyday work, namely the item 'easy to use' (ad= 0,44), usability in everyday work (ad= 0,22), navigation in the app (ad= 0,33) as well as its intuitive use (ad= 0,22) scored a median rating of 4 or 'good' with the average absolute deviation from the median being relatively low (under 0,5). Hence, overall the participants were content with the app as shown in the first tabletop exercise.

The usability of the app was only rated by the majority of the participants in two items: both the opportunity to respond to missing cases in a timely manner with the help of the ChildRescue app (ad= 0,56) as well as the ability to establish relevant locations of missing children (ad= 0,56) was given a mean rating of 4, equalling 'good'. The slightly increased deviation for both items could be due to the fact that the participants of the focus group held various positions within the organisation and their subjective estimation of the usefulness of the app in future work can differ. The other items 'organising volunteers', 'recruiting new volunteers', 'increasing the speed of recovery', and 'matching old similar cases to new cases' were answered with 'I don't know' by the majority of the participants, indicating that the described workflows, such as recruiting new volunteers, may be in the responsibility of other staff members that did not participate in the tabletop exercise or are organised differently. Therefore, the survey will be revised before the second piloting phase to improve identifying the workflows of Child Focus and enabling the participants to rate all or most items with a score.

When evaluating the accessibility of the ChildRescue platform, the data protection (n= 2) and the audibility of the audio signals (n= 3) were, much like in the evaluation of the app, also not scored by the majority of the participants. This indicates that the data protection protocols should be discussed in more detail in the next piloting phase to ensure the participants' confidence in rating them. The lack of knowledge on the audio signals could be due to the smartphone's settings, which should not be put on silent mode during the next piloting exercise. Additionally, the majority of participants chose 'I don't know' when answering the item 'understandable for volunteers' (n= 3). This lack of scoring might be due to the fact that no volunteers were involved in the first tabletop exercise and thus, the participants were unsure about their ease in understanding the platform.

The usability of the platform in responding quickly to missing cases (ad= 0,14), establishing relevant locations of missing children (ad= 0,44) and creating case reports with the aid of the platform (ad= 0,29) all received median ratings of 4 or 'good' with low average absolute deviations from the median, indicating a high consistency in the answers of the participants. The remaining items 'organising volunteers' (n= 2), 'increasing the speed of the recovery of missing children' (n= 2), and 'matching old similar cases to new cases' (n= 4) were answered by the majority of the participants with 'I don't know', which might indicate a difference in the workflow of Child Focus in comparison to the other two piloting organisations that should be taken into account for the design of the survey of the second piloting phase.

The same conclusion can be drawn from the multiple 'I don't know' answers in the last set of questions that focus on the time needed for specific workflows without the use of the ChildRescue tools. The lack of scores in that part of the survey could indicate that the work practice in Child Focus is somewhat distinct from Smile of the Child and Hellenic Red Cross, which in turn could be due to different legal frameworks in Belgium in comparison to Greece.

The average time to get informed about a case was indicated to lie between two and five hours with answers ranking from zero to one hour to 16 or more hours. This high variation in the answers could be due to the different involvement of the participants with the publication of missing reports and their resulting perspective of the speed. The average time needed to complete case reports received a median rating of zero to one hour, with answers varying from zero to one hour to eleven to 15 hours. However, due to the difference in paperwork involved in different positions at Child Focus, this discrepancy is to be expected. The average time for between the reporting and recovery of a missing child (n= 3), the formation of a volunteer search and rescue team (n= 2), and for the retrieval of information on old and similar cases (n= 4) as well as the average number of old cases matched to current cases (n= 3) and the investigation activities in irrelevant locations (n= 0) have been answered with 'I don't know' by the majority of the participants, except for n. These high rates of non-score answers from the participants in Belgium makes a partial revision of the survey before the second piloting phase necessary to ensure all partners' operational practices are reflected and represented in the items of the survey.

In order to capture a more in-depth understanding of the participants' view on the ChildRescue tools, a focus group was held in addition to the survey discussed above. **The focus group participants from Child Focus agreed that the app and platform are overall user friendly and instinctive to use, thereby enabling the broader public to use the app without the need for a deeper understanding or knowledge of technology.** The participants expressed hope that the public will

feel more involved with the missing cases through the use of the app and its notification. However, the potential issue of abuse of the app was raised, since offenders could seek out vulnerable youth in their area and target them specifically with the use of the information supplied by the app (such as the name, photo, age etc.). The low-threshold of the app was thus characterised as ambiguous, since it might involve people who would have otherwise not taken notice of the missing child but the easily available information could also be used ill-intentionally. In order to reduce the risk, it was suggested to lift the complete anonymous status of people who want to send in information on the missing child by having them provide a phone number or their postal address for police or Case Managers to contact them in the future. One participant proposed to automatically fill in the SIM card information of people who send information on specific cases. Yet, the privacy of the data with regard to third parties should be guaranteed to entice a response. However, even if the privacy of the data from third parties can be ensured, this measure will lower the willingness of the public to come forward, which the participants identified as a necessary trade-off for the safety of the missing children. Additionally, the possibility to 'flag' people by surveilling the way users utilise the app and identifying those who only show interest in certain age groups or gender. However, the risk of actual abuse was considered to be low and the commonly used systems at the moment, such as sharing a missing poster on Facebook carry the same risks as the appeal on the app. Therefore, collecting some basic information on the people who want to report information on a missing child would be enough in order to ensure potential offenders can be traced after having used the app. Users should be restricted to be people above a certain age, to exclude children from the app. Furthermore, there should be a pop-up window with the information that the GPS tracking on the phone needs to be activated at all times (not just for the registering) in order for the app to work. Another potential risk that was flagged by the focus group was that the lack of effort could also prompt a false spotting out of boredom. As a validation mechanism, it was suggested to cross check the ChildRescue alert sightings with the responses to the paper publications that are already employed by Child Focus. Also, the information on the child should be somewhat limited, i.e. not giving the full name but rather only the first name.

There were some practical issues with the design that were pointed out as well. Namely, some of the lines in the app and platform are not completely visible, but break off after the start of the sentence, i.e. at the arrival at the facility: 'if the child has been-'. This should be altered to increase the usability of the platform. School issues should be added to the reasons of disappearance and the option to check multiple reasons should be implemented. Psychological disorder should be rephrased, since it might be too stigmatising. Also, the possibility to save a new case during its creation without publishing it would ease the process for the Case Managers, if they have to look up additional information. Hence, the save button should be visible at all times during the creation of an alert. There should be more options given for the different social media outlets, i.e. Snapchat, Instagram and also the possibility to indicate multiple social media platforms. If multiple Case Managers are working on the same case by inputting information, the risk of overwriting one another exists, which should be addressed. One solution could be to only enable one Case Manager at a time to edit case information. The haircut should be added to the description of the missing child as well as additional sociodemographic information on the child, such as the languages spoken, the postal code of their home, and potential disputes between parents and the child. Also, as mentioned in the other focus groups as well, the input fields of the platform should have an explanation with the exact kind of information that is needed to enable Case Managers as well as family members to fill it out in a unified fashion. In order to incentivise the users to engage

more with the cases, it might also be helpful to give information on why and when an alert was deactivated.

The interface that can only be seen by Case Managers should give information on the number of previous ChildRescue alerts for the same child along with details of the old cases, such as case type and how it was resolved. Also, since Belgium is a multi-lingual country, alerts should be fashioned at least in French and Dutch without the need to create multiple case files in different languages. The additional option to download previews of alerts to send to colleagues could be helpful in distributing information among NGOs faster. During the presentation of the app, closed cases were displayed higher than active ones in the app. This should be revised to ensure that active cases are displayed on top, with resolved cases on the bottom.

The usability of the platform and app was seen as high by the participants, since the use is very intuitive. **However, the success of the platform and app in comparison to the traditional alerts in place now needs to be demonstrated to the staff members as well as to the users rather quickly in order to ensure that their motivation to use this tool instead of other existing solutions remains high.** Therefore, the active nature of being able to give testimony should be stressed for the users, since this sets it apart from other existing solutions. Also, the geotargeting in combination with the alerts might trigger more interest since it involves people more directly. In order to maintain a high level of interest, the already implemented function of being able to follow a case for registered users was seen as instrumental, but it should also be available if the user leaves the radius of the case alert, since they might already be emotionally invested and want to know the outcome. The future of the alerts was assessed to be more likely anchored in digital solutions such as ChildRescue, which enable users to report sightings through the push of a button rather than paper posters that need to be read to know the hotline number that can then be called in case of sightings. However, in order to ensure the data protection of the digital files, NGOs should only be able to access their own files, unless the NGO decides to send the case to other organisations, like in cases of international parental abductions. In terms of implementation, it was noted that only the police will be able to decide which sightings should be considered credible and thus, the search and rescue parties have to wait for their commands.

The results from the focus group thus show a highly positive overall view of the ChildRescue tools, albeit the very detailed discussion of features of the app and platform revealed some points that need revision. The confusion over some distinct aspects of the data protection protocol was mirrored by the answers in the surveys and explaining this in more detail should consequently be one of the central talking points in the second tabletop exercises. Additionally, some differences in the workflows of the involved organisations should be taken into consideration more to develop an app as well as an evaluation methodology that accurately gathers data and opinions from all piloting partners.

4.3.3 ChildRescue KPIs based on Pilot

The relevant KPI values, as formed from the execution of the first pilot phase, are enlisted in the following table.

Table 4-2 KPIs for Child Focus based on first Pilot Phase

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value	KPI Value after 1st Pilot
PI.01	number of ChildRescue mobile application downloads monthly	N/A	0	13
PI.02	number of aggregated ChildRescue mobile application downloads	N/A	0	13
PI.05	number of notifications sent through ChildRescue and opened	N/A	0	8
PI.06	average number of citizens providing feedback per case	average number of citizens providing feedback per case before mobile application launch	3 testimonies	4
PI.07	average number of citizens providing feedback through the ChildRescue app per case	N/A	0	4
PI.09	ratio: average number of citizens receiving notification through ChildRescue to total number of mobile application downloads per case	N/A	0	8/13
PI.10	ratio: number of notifications sent to specific locations to total number of notifications	N/A	0	1
PI.11	ratio: number of relevant (in the context of ChildRescue terminology) feedback	N/A	0	4/4

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Value	KPI Value after 1 st Pilot
	to total number of submitted feedback			
PI.12	ratio: number of mobile app users who visited the relevant informative section in ChildRescue app (Do's & Don'ts, how to respond in case of child neglect, abuse etc.)	N/A	0	5

4.4 Challenges and Next Steps

The main two challenges, to which an answer is to be found, are (as described above):

- 1) Find an easy to use technical solution to extract testimonies from the platform in order to be able to send them to the police
- 2) Find a technical solution that answers the need for the possibility of bilingualism. Especially the option of being able to edit the alert before launching it, appears an important solution.

The main next steps are the following:

- 1) In the following weeks and months, we will have to invest a lot of time and effort to integrate the ChildRescue in our existing procedures.
- 2) In the next pilot phase, the collaborative space will be tested in order to investigate whether we will be able to use it with our volunteers and/or specifically identified partners such as structural partners (e.g. taxi drivers, security guards) or the police.

5 Pilot 3: Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors – Greece

5.1 Pilot Scenario

Main Hypothesis: ChildRescue platform is used in parallel to regular REDCROSS registration of Unaccompanied Migrant Children (UMC). ChildRescue platform contributes in the REDCROSS search & discovery of UMC activities.

Overall places involved: REDCROSS hosting facility for UMC at Alkiviadou str. Athens, REDCROSS hosting facility in Volos, REDCROSS Multifunctional Center (MFC) in Athens, REDCROSS Tracing service, REDCROSS Branch in Kos island, REDCROSS Branch in Piraeus.

Total Number of persons involved: 7 for tabletop, 25 for simulation exercise.

All role-plays involved are performed by the REDCROSS staff and volunteers. Multidiscipline (trans-sector) approach.

Economy of the scenarios: the tabletop exercise works as a preparatory phase for the field/real-time simulation scenario.

Assumptions:

- When first entering a hosting facility those UMC (of age above 15) consent to Search & Rescue (SAR) in case of emergency (i.e. manmade or natural hazard).
- The UMC who consented are profiled by the facility manager with ChildRescue.
- The REDCROSS with the management of the corresponding REDCROSS UMC facility (in cooperation to State stakeholders and using the REDCROSS network: the TS/RFL and the MFC) tries to re-establish and maintain contact between the hosted UMC and his/her family wherever it is.
- All data registration, activities and information sharing are done on the basis of the best interest of the child and in full respect to Red Cross fundamental Principles.

Aim 1: UMC accommodated with the REDCROSS are registered with ChildRescue. Access of users to ChildRescue is confirmed on different levels.

Step 1: 12 UMC are registered by the responsible social and case workers (Hosting Facility Manager) with the REDCROSS hosting facilities in Volos (5 children) and Attica (7 children)

Step 2: Organisation Coordinator confirm full access to the registered information

Step 3: The facility manager in Attica receives a note from EKKA (National Center for Social Solidarity) about a new placement coming from Volos facility and requests the transfer of the case profile via CR

Step 4: Organisation Coordinator user with the Social Welfare Division (SWD) of the REDCROSS greenlights and confirms the transfer

Step 5: A REDCROSS TS/RFL case worker registers an UMC for whom there is a tracing request within the REDCROSS

Step 6: Advanced users confirm a match between the UMC registered by the REDCROSS TS/RFL case worker and the data base of the facility in Attica

Step 7: Organisation Coordinator with the REDCROSS Restore Family Links asks REDCROSS on Kos Island (according to data from UMCs file) to send additional information. By cross-checking information, the positive outcome of the search is confirmed.

Preparatory work: Development of 12 fake cases of UMC for registration and creation of 3 facilities (Attica, Volos, Kos)

5.2 Scenario Execution

Table 5-1 Overview of the tabletop exercise conducted by REDCROSS

Tabletop	
Time schedule	11 th October 2019
Platform release	1.0
Actors: 20 in total	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simple Users (Registered user): 3 persons - Organisation Case Managers: 3 persons - Organisation Facility Managers: 3 persons - Organisation Coordinator Managers: 2 persons - Visitors: 3 persons Presence, support and training by representatives of the technical partners (3 people), the project coordinator (NTUA – 2 people) and MADE (1 person)

The Tabletop exercise took place on the 11th of October, 2019, at the training venue of the REDCROSS Social Welfare Dpt., at Voulis 38. The occasion of the tabletop exercise served also as an introduction to the ChildRescue platform and a training opportunity for the REDCROSS employees involved, as it is reflected on the relative agenda.

The actual exercise was organised in different parts according to the different actions foreseen for the REDCROSS with ChildRescue platform:

- Registration of UMC entering a REDCROSS facility (profiling) and monitoring of their presence
- Transfer of data between two facilities
- Integration of the ChildRescue platform to a tracing procedure

Thursday October 11 th , 2019			
Agenda			
09:00-09:30	<i>Arrival – registration Welcome Coffee</i>		
09:30-9:45	I.0	Agenda - Introduction	HRC
9:45-10:45	L1	Presentation of the Child Rescue Platform & app	NTUA, HRC, Suite5
10:45-11:15	<i>Coffee break</i>		
11:15-13:00	L2	Table top exercise & parallel training	HRC, SLG, UBITECH, Suite5
13:00-14:00	<i>Light lunch break</i>		
14:00-15:00	L3	Recap & identification of necessary modifications (if any)	HRC, SLG, UBITECH, Suite5, NTUA
15:00-15:30	L4	Presentation of the future functionalities	UBITECH, Suite5
15:30-16:00	<i>Coffee break</i>		
16:00-17:00	L5	Discussion, Evaluation & Wrapping up	HRC, Suite5, NTUA, UBITECH, SLG

Figure 5-1 Pilot Meeting Agenda

The procedure involved three main places of interest: The REDCROSS hosting facility in Athens, the hosting facility in Volos, the hosting facility in Kalavryta and the Tracing Service, under the **Main Hypothesis** that the ChildRescue platform is used in parallel to regular REDCROSS registration of UMC and that the ChildRescue platform contributes to the REDCROSS search and discovery of UMC mechanisms.

For the economy of the scenarios: the tabletop exercise has been planned to work as a preparatory phase for the field/real-time simulation scenario, while certain assumptions were made:

- When first entering the Shelter those UMC of age (above 15) consent to Search & Rescue (SAR) in case of emergency
- The UMC who consent are profiled by the shelter manager with ChildRescue
- When an UMC is placed in a REDCROSS hosting facility there are made efforts to restore contact with their family members
- All data registration and information sharing are done on the basis of the best interest of the child and in full respect to REDCROSS fundamental principles

The first part of the pilot involved training on the ChildRescue platform and simulating integrating the ChildRescue platform in the profiling procedure once an UMC enters a REDCROSS hosting facility (placement by order of the Social Solidarity Center of the Ministry of Labor – in Greek E.K.K.A.). The relative procedure is presented in Figure 5-2.

Part 1: Profiling & Monitoring

Figure 5-2 Profiling Stage

Simulating Data registration:

Once a placement order is issued for an UMC, the receiving organisation - in that case the REDCROSS - receives together with the child all relative legal documentation. This information is on a later stage updated by the facility's social services to include further to the personal details and the legal background of the concerned UMC, his/her psychosocial background and best interest assessment details, as well as social media accounts and phone-numbers of both the UMC and his/her family members that can be in touch with. Gradual updating of the profiling information is required.

To simulate the procedure 12 anonymised cases were chosen and 12 full case-files were created with profiling information as described above. To preserve anonymisation, false names and personal details were used, while to better serve the hypothesis each case file came with a paper doll, some with distinctive physical features and clothing, representing the respective UMC involved.

Figure 5-3 Individual UMC profiles

All participants were split in pairs and each pair, representing a hosting facility, received two individual cases to simulate profiling through the ChildRescue platform. Data registration went on well and some users uploaded also photos of the paper-dolls on the ChildRescue app.

The list created at each facility level could also be considered as a monitoring list enabling the caregivers to check the presence of the UMC on daily basis. The total of registrations, however, should be visible only on Organisation Coordinators level (two persons). By referring to the monitoring list, caregivers in the scenario could track the absence of an UMC during the first counting of the day and initiate procedures before the UMC was declared missing (second counting) – when an alert had been initiated and the UMC's place with the facility was considered vacant.

Part 2: Data Transfer

One problem of the profiling procedure is that it has to be repeated on different levels (authorities, NGOs, within an organisation etc.) Each hosting facility is keeping its own files and one of the scopes of profiling with ChildRescue is also to easily transfer data between facilities when needed. In the framework of the tabletop exercise, the REDCROSS received a note from EKKA, informing them that one of the UMC, reported missing from the hosting facility in Attica (during the a/m monitoring procedure), was found and has been relocated in Volos hosting facility. The Facility Manager in Attica was asked to transfer the profiling information of the UMC concerned to Volos facility. The coordinator of the organisation validated the request and green-lighted the transfer (orally as the respective part of the app was not ready) and the profiling data were successfully made available to the other facility environment.

Figure 5-4 Picture from the pilot exercise at REDCROSS

Part 3: Missing Child Search coordinating services and activities (multiple access levels)

The final part of the tabletop exercise was simulated on paper as the ChildRescue application encountered a technical difficulty.

According to the scenario the Tracing Service of the REDCROSS received a request about a missing child from the regional REDCROSS Department on Kos Island. While profiling the missing child using the ChildRescue platform, however, the case worker found out that there was a potential match with one of the UMC in the REDCROSS hosting facilities (one of the 12 UMC initially registered). This has not been tested between different organisations at this stage through the ChildRescue platform but this is planned for the field exercise (2nd pilot phase).

The second pilot phase also involves active research, with the ChildRescue assistance, to which certified REDCROSS volunteers will participate; enabling to use the whole spectrum of research coordinating capacity with ChildRescue, as shown in Figure 5-5.

Figure 5-5 Research Coordination Methodology for REDCROSS

5.3 Pilot Evaluation

5.3.1 Main Outcomes

The overall experience was positive with good potentials for future use under conditions. The main concerns had to do with the data protection issues and the legal implications, given that the REDCROSS pilot is dedicated to UMC and there are certain restrictions deriving from the relative ICRC legacy. The guardianship of the UMC in Greece remains a key issue and social workers working with the REDCROSS shelters underlined that the validation of data use should probably be on state level. It is also noted that ChildRescue could offer a great opportunity to unify data on different organisational levels, i.e. internally in the organisation. However, there is a concern on how sharing of information with other organisations would work. Social workers were also concerned about having to duplicate entries on different levels.

Informal follow-up discussions among the partners involved would be good to take place before moving to the next steps.

From the REDCROSS side it would be good to consider repeating the tabletop exercise once the relative part of the app is ready, to be able to provide the pilot with a more accurate evaluation of the app.

5.3.2 Feedback Analysis

A focus group and surveys were conducted with nine participants at the REDCROSS during the first tabletop exercise. The participants of the tabletop exercise at the REDCROSS (N= 9) indicated the lowest overall median scores throughout the surveys of all three piloting organisations.

While evaluating the app, both the understandability for staff members (ad= 0,67) and volunteers (ad= 0,33) as well as the colour (ad= 0,56), size (ad= 0,78) and contrasting of the text (ad= 0,78), the

audibility of the alarms (ad= 0,57) and the use of the app (navigation in app ad= 0,5; easy to use ad= 0,33; protecting sensitive data ad = 0,89; usability in everyday work ad= 0,22) all received a median rating of 'good' or 4. However, the higher average absolute deviation from the median of the items 'features are understandable for staff members', 'colour of text', 'contrast between text and background', 'alarm signals are audible' and 'protecting sensitive data', which were all bigger than 0,5 indicates that some more work might be needed in those areas. Specifically, the design of the app regarding text size, colours and contrasting should be accessible to people with visual impairments. For example, using green and red shades – especially within the same field, can be challenging for people with dyschromatopsia. Similarly, while the alarm signals may have not been audible due to the settings of the specific phones, audio signals should be easily heard. In contrast to the design aspects of the app, the participants may have benefited from additional explanations regarding the data protection regime of the app and all features that staff members might use since the answers were spread on these topics as well. The intuitive use of the app received a median score of 3,5 or 'okay-good' with an average absolute deviation from the median of 0,88. This relatively high score can be explained by the deviation being in between categories, which means that every answer must deviate from the mean since 3,5 was not a possible answer. Furthermore, individual technological affinity might play a role in how intuitive an app is perceived.

The usability of the ChildRescue app was mostly rated as 'okay', equalling a 3. The items 'establishing relevant locations of missing children', 'increasing the speed of recovery', and 'organising volunteers' all had average absolute deviation scores of 0,5, showcasing only a slight difference in the perception of the participants. The recruitment of new volunteers through the app (ad= 0,56) and the timely response to missing cases (ad= 0,57) received slightly higher scores in the average absolute deviation from the median. This indicates that the opportunities to recruit volunteers may not have been showcased convincingly, which should be taken into consideration for the second tabletop exercise. Furthermore, the lack of agreement on the possibility to respond quickly to missing cases might be caused by the nature of the work of the REDCROSS, which often encounters natural disasters in their work, such as earthquakes, which can lead to chaotic circumstances that would make the timely use of the app unlikely. Only the item 'matching old similar cases to new ones' was rated slightly higher with a median of 3,5 or 'okay-good' and an average absolute deviation from the median of 0,63, indicating that the participants were not in complete agreement. This could be due to their different positions within the organisation and their resulting varying work experience in handling old cases.

In regard to the platform, the data protection had the lowest median score of 'okay' or 3, with an average absolute deviation from the median of 0,89. While there was a relatively wide spread of answers ranging from 2, equalling 'bad' to 5, equalling 'very good', it appears that the data protection protocols should be revisited in the second tabletop exercise to improve the overall understanding of the measures by all participants. The size of the text (ad= 0,75) as well as the comprehensibility for staff members (ad= 0,75) both showed median rating of 'okay-good', namely 3,5. This should be revised before the second tabletop exercise to ensure the design of the platform as well as the app are inclusive and the participants receive enough training to feel confident in the use of the platform and app by staff members and volunteers. All remaining items received median scores of 4, equalling 'good'. For the colour of the text (ad= 0,625) as well as its contrast (ad= 0,875) and the comprehensibility for volunteers (ad= 0,57), the average absolute deviation from the median reached over 0,5, indicating an

ambiguity between the participants. Hence, the design of the platform as well as the app should be revised to ensure that it is accessible to everybody.

Additionally, there will be a higher focus on the volunteers in the second tabletop exercise, which could help to resolve the high variation in the answers on the comprehensibility of the platform for the staff members.

The usability of the platform received overall higher median scores than the app. The three items 'organising volunteers' (ad= 0,44), 'timely response to missing cases' (ad= 0,44), and 'increasing the speed of recovery' (ad= 0,5) received median scores of 'okay' or 3 with low average absolute deviation from the median (all <0,5), indicating a high overall agreement between participants. The remaining items 'matching old similar cases to new cases' (ad= 0,63), 'establishing relevant locations of missing children' (ad= 0,63) and 'creating case reports' (ad= 0,63) all had a median score of 3,5 or 'okay-good'. The answers varied from 'okay' to 'very good', which could be due to the different positions held by the participants within the REDCROSS and their resulting perspectives or work experience in these specific areas.

The last set of questions relating to the work of the REDCROSS at the moment – without the use of the ChildRescue tools – has only yielded one item with the majority of answers being 'I don't know', namely 'number of investigation activities in irrelevant locations' (n= 3), which might indicate the necessity to rephrase this item for the next surveys. All of the other items showed an average absolute deviation from the median that was higher than 0,5. However, since these are estimations of the time it takes to achieve certain goals or the number of cases, a higher deviation is to be expected as it is highly subjective and can also be influenced by the participant's own unique work experience. The average time between the reporting and recovery of a missing child was reported as 16 or more hours, with only one participant disagreeing and indicating zero to one hour. The average time passed before citizens first receive information on a case was mostly ranked as 16 or more hours with answers ranging from two to five to 16 or more hours. The average time for the formation of a volunteer search and rescue team was indicated to be six to ten hours, with answers ranging from two to five to 16 or more hours. Both the average number of old cases matched to a new case as well as the average time needed to retrieve information from old similar cases in hours was indicated to lie between two and five with answers varying between zero to one to six to ten hours. Lastly, the median of the average time needed to create a case report was indicated to lie between zero to one and one to five hours, with individual answers ranking from zero to one hour to 16 or more hours. The unusually high deviation might stem from the different positions held by the participants within the REDCROSS and their resulting time capacities to file reports promptly. Yet, these numbers shall serve as a point for comparison to the later responses in the second piloting phase when the ChildRescue tools are being utilised.

In addition to the surveys, participants of the tabletop exercise also had the opportunity to elaborate in more detail throughout the focus group that was conducted with them. The overall sentiment toward the app and platform was described as positive, however, there were some concerns with regard to data protection since the REDCROSS works primarily with the highly vulnerable group of unaccompanied migrant minors and thus needs to ensure a high standard of data protection for them.

Yet, ChildRescue could also be seen as an opportunity for this work, since it offers the chance to create a unified data collection within the organisation and thereby could improve the reaction to missing unaccompanied migrant minors. The data protection protocols that have been put in place should consequently be made more visible in the next tabletop exercise to enable a better understanding of them for the participants. Additionally, some more detailed comments regarding possible changes to the app and platform were made that shall now be described.

Regarding the input options of the platform, there should be an added option of 'unknown' and 'other' along an open comment box for some input boxes, such as the psychological status or the reason for the disappearance. The phrasing should be revised in some sections as well: psychological status could be renamed into psychosocial status alongside an open comment box since the minors might be facing manifold issues. Additionally, the reason for disappearance should only be displayed as the 'most likely' reason since there is never a complete certainty that the child was categorised correctly. In the health section, chronic diseases and needed medication should be added since this might be vital information for the Case Managers. The section 'drug user' should be replaced with a more politically correct term. The Global Commission on Drug Policy's report (2017) suggests using 'substance use disorder' instead of 'drug habit' [2]. It should however be noted that the platform and especially the app should remain comprehensible for the public, so that the potentially stigmatising effects need to be weighed against literacy. Another remark about the input fields was that including the religion of an unaccompanied migrant minor might be stigmatising, but could also give clues about the potential locations of interest (such as nearby churches, mosques or synagogues etc.). Furthermore, the person filling in the last known location of the unaccompanied migrant minor that went missing has to be the legal guardian due to the specific requirements of the REDCROSS. Since there is often not a concrete date of birth available for the missing migrant minors, an age field that allows for some leniency should be added. If the child themselves own a phone, the number would be useful. However, adding phone numbers of relatives that might be in contact with the child are also essential. The Case Manager should be enabled to update existing alerts instead of having to create new ones.

Concerning the app, a pop-up window in case users send in insufficient information on a missing child was suggested. There were other notes on the app that were also mentioned in the Smile of the Child focus group, such as the issue with the menu not being available, thus rendering the user without movement in the app. Another repeated criticism was the fact that the GDPR information is displayed in the process of registering instead of before the registration.

For the organisation, benefits lie mostly in the enhanced speed, namely in the possibility to quickly create alerts electronically and in a unified fashion. This simplifies the transfer of information on missing children from one shelter to another and thereby advances the child's protection by making the coordination easier. Yet, despite the general positive attitude toward the ChildRescue app and platform, the necessity of training of the volunteers in the use of the app through a fictional scenario before they are working on real cases was indicated, which should be taken into consideration. Also, informal follow-up discussion among the piloting partners should be facilitated before the second phase of the piloting is initiated to ensure that the partners are in agreement. Since the REDCROSS-specific use scenario of the app was not yet ready at the time of the first tabletop exercise, its compliance to the ICRC code of conduct in regard to data registration and use needs to be evaluated in the second piloting phase. The

REDCROSS would welcome to be able to use different levels of the app for the different users within the organisation, which is already in planning and should be implemented as well as showcased in the second piloting phase.

5.3.3 ChildRescue KPIs based on Pilot

A set of relevant KPI values as formed from the execution of the first pilot phase, are enlisted in the following table. The operations of REDCROSS are not always open to the general public and discreet investigations are conducted by volunteers of the REDCROSS.

Table 5-2 KPIs for REDCROSS based on first Pilot Phase

PI #	Performance Indicator Description	Baseline Calculation Approach	Baseline Values	KPI Value after 1 st Pilot Phase
PI.01	number of ChildRescue mobile application downloads monthly	N/A	0	13
PI.02	number of aggregated ChildRescue mobile application downloads	N/A	0	13
PI.12	ratio: number of mobile app users who visited the relevant informative section in ChildRescue app (Do's & Don'ts, how to respond in case of child neglect, abuse etc.)	N/A	0	5

5.4 Challenges and Next Steps

The ChildRescue platform aims to be used in parallel to the REDCROSS mechanisms offering a new asset to the organisation's multidisciplinary approach towards a more efficient and effective solution for UMC, by contributing to prevention of disappearance, improving time-management and providing a tool that will reinforce coordination, decision making and information sharing on different organisational levels (hosting facilities, Tracing Service, Management, regional REDCROSS Departments, etc.).

As the configured parts of the ChildRescue app for the REDCROSS were not ready, the tabletop exercise took place with the use of the main ChildRescue app and focused on profiling and data transfer. In general, the time-schedule was kept as planned and, with the exception of a technical problem that appeared during the last part of the exercise, the whole procedure was smooth and fruitful.

Profiling of UMC has proved to be an easy process – although certain profile parts need to be amended – and it also enables hosting facilities keeping an easily updated monitoring list of hosted UMC. The e-monitoring list offers a new potential for communication and coordination to the care-givers and the facility manager also keeping better track of the hosted UMC within a certain facility and providing accurate and on time information to the centre of operations. When there is any change of the unaccompanied minor's status, relevant actors could be informed through the platform. The Tracing Service will, equally, be able to search the UMC records and immediately retrieve all required information to enable positive matches.

Of course, those capacities could only be discussed theoretically during the pilot, as the different levels of access for the REDCROSS were not ready yet, however, access to the information on different organisational levels was valid as a helpful cooperation tool skipping the heavy bureaucracy complications.

There was some concern expressed about whether the use of the ChildRescue platform would result in doubling the work of involved staff, taking into consideration that there is already a number of databases available with the REDCROSS that should be updated. Thus, prioritisation and better coordination of activities are required to efficiently use ChildRescue and take advantage of it. Being able to transfer available information about the UMC through a unified e-environment, will help to avoid multiple registrations and duplicates. It will also reduce needed paperwork whenever a UMC is transported to another hosting facility, as the record of the minor will be instantly become available to the new facility. This will save time and ensure the consistency of information shared between facilities.

There are also major concerns with regard to having to the access of confidential information collected from the REDCROSS about a UMC to unauthorised personnel that are users of the platform. Such concerns are related to data protection and ownership of the available information issues, underlining that the REDCROSS environment within the ChildRescue platform should be secured to ensure that the private information of the UMC should be protected and the do no Harm principle would be fully respected. Still the REDCROSS should be able to share information with other actors by its own initiative and decision and only for the vital interest of the UMC. It should be also possible to erase all information on an UMC profile, if needed.

Today, communication with and among REDCROSS volunteers is mainly done by phone, which restricts the types and the immediacy of information that can be shared. Real-time information sharing -including photos and multimedia- and location monitoring, although not tested with the REDCROSS yet, could provide a new potential to volunteer mobilisation and coordination and might also contribute to improve cross border cooperation in the near future.

Last but not least, it has been highlighted that, especially when it comes to UMC, research should not end with their discovery, and that the ChildRescue initiative should be accompanied with a protection follow-up mechanism that will ensure the best interest of the UMC and after it is traced.

6 Conclusions

During the first tabletop exercise, the key personnel of the three pilot organisations had the opportunity to familiarise with the ChildRescue platform, use its value-adding features and experience how ChildRescue can be integrated in their existing procedures. Furthermore, the participants provided invaluable feedback on the implemented mobile and web application. The execution of the pilot exercise served another purpose: testing the platform in a controlled environment that simulates real-life situations. Thus, the 'tabletop exercise' is the umbrella term for the complete first round of testing, which includes both the demonstration of the app and platform to staff members of the pilot organisation, as well as the evaluation of the content presented, in the form of a focus group and surveys.

After the execution of the exercise, the participants generally showed a positive attitude towards the ChildRescue platform and were willing to adopt it in their work. Some of the benefits of ChildRescue identified by the participants were the enhancement of fast information exchange with the alerts and team coordination tools, the simplification of information transfer between hosting facilities, the promotion of public engagement and the easier identification of irrelevant incoming information (i.e. spam). It has been also noted that although there are organisational differences among the pilot partners, the ChildRescue app has been designed in such a generic and modular way, that it can fit to any organisation of the field, covering a large part of their work. Regarding user experience, all three organisations agreed that 'in-app navigation' and 'understandability of application features' were excellent, although some notes were made regarding corrections in the wording and design, especially with regards to accessibility – i.e. size of text, contrasting of text colour with background and size of displayed photos). SoC participants gave the highest overall ratings of the app and platform when compared to the other two piloting organisations, while the Child Focus group showed the highest rate in 'I don't know' answers. This should be highly taken into consideration, as it could indicate unclear phrasing or use of technical terminology. It has also been noted that organisational differences in procedures were not fully reflected in the surveys. As a result, surveys for the second pilot exercise will be adapted to ensure phrasing is understood by all participants and fully covers the individual workflows of each organisation. Lastly, the necessity to adequately train volunteers and staff members in the use of the ChildRescue platform and application has been highlighted. Fitting scenarios should be drafted by the pilot organisations for this purpose.

Feedback of users on technical aspects of the ChildRescue platform will be appropriately assessed and handled by the technical partners in the context of WP3. It is possible that not all proposed changes are applicable to the platform at this stage of development or may not be of essential added-value for all organisations. Furthermore, for the preparation of the second pilot phase, the evaluation methodology of the pilots should be adapted according to the results of the feedback analysis from the focus group and surveys. This involves revising the questionnaires and pilot guidelines. The updated methodology will be included in D4.4 – "ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release II". The second release of this deliverable, with the documentation and results of the second pilot phase is planned for [M34] in D4.5 – "ChildRescue Pilot Experimentation Documentation Release II".

Annex I: References

- [1] Performance Based Management Special Interest Group (2001). The performance-based management handbook. Establishing and maintaining a performance-based management program (Vol. 1). Oak Ridge, TN, USA: US Department of Energy and Oak Ridge Associated Universities
- [2] Global Commission on Drug Policy (2017): The world drug perception problem. Countering prejudices about people who use drugs. GCDP.